

Pest resistance – diseases

Reaction of rice germplasm to leaf blast (BL) in West Bengal

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We tested 496 rice varieties and lines for resistance to leaf BL caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. in hot-spot areas under weather conditions conducive to disease during 1983 and 1985 wet seasons at Kalimpong and 1987 and

Reaction of rice cultivars to BL.

Cultivar	Cross	Disease score ^a
IET7293	Ponni mutant	0
IET6658	Nira/TN1	2
IET7590	RP5-32/Pankaj	0
IET6010	IR8/W1263	3
IET2254	T90/IR8	0
IET2815	TKM6/IR8	3
IET2233	Beli Patna/IR6	3
IET8669	Ratna/Jachum white	0
Munal	CI 5310 (Introduction from USA)	2
NC507	Pureline selection	4
NC513	Pureline selection	4
NC493	Selection from Najani	0
IR54		0
IR42		3
CN835-2-9-4-11	IR20 mutant	3
CN701-1-8	Kumargore/Jalaplaba//CR1002	0
CN695-2-17	CN540/IET6213	1
CN506-147-142	IR30/Leb Mue Nahng III/IR1514A-E 666	3
CN844-94-8-13	IR36/Jaya	3
CN840-9-1-A	IR50/IR36	3
CN849-77	Patnai 23/Bhasamanik	1
CN840-9-1-B	IR50/IR36	3
CN772-4	IET2895/CB1	3
CN772-6-1	IET2895/CB1	0
CN772-6-3	IET2895/CB1	0
CN722-1	CB1/Ratna	3
CN722-8	CB1/Ratna	0
CN722-3	CB1/Ratna	3
CN741-2-1	Jaya/Latisail	0
CN936-5-1	CB1 mutant	1
CN936-5-2	CB1 mutant	1
CN936-5-3	CB1 mutant	1
CN937-6-3	IR50 mutant	3
CN937-6-6	IR50 mutant	3
CB1		0
Latisail		7
Pusa 2-21	Susceptible checks	8
IR50		8

^a By the Standard evaluation system for rice.

1988 dry seasons at Pandua. Test entries included 45 mutants of CBI and 34 of Latisail.

Nursery beds were fertilized with 20-22 kg NP/ha. Three rows of susceptible checks Pusa 2-21 and IR50 surrounded the nursery beds.

Under high disease pressure, 34 lines showed resistance to moderate resistance to leaf BL (see table). Fifty percent of CB1 mutants and 90% of Latisail mutants (data not shown) gave resistant reaction when CB1 was resistant and Latisail was susceptible to leaf BL. ■

Rapid screening for rice tungro resistance using viruliferous green leafhopper (GLH) nymphs

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GLH *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) nymphs can efficiently transmit tungro

viruses to rice seedlings, and are easier to handle than adults for germplasm screening. Nymphs can be produced in large numbers using simple rearing procedures.

Gravid GLH females were caged for 3-4 d on 50-d-old tungro-infected TN1 rice plants for egg-laying (Fig. 1). One week later, 15-20 seeds each of rice varieties for test were sown in a 110- × 65- × 5-cm aluminum seedbox in 10-cm-long rows, 4.5 cm apart. Each seedbox contained 130 rows of seedlings.

At 7 d after sowing, the seedbox was placed in a 240- × 75- × 30-cm galvanized-iron tray. The last seedling in each row was enclosed in a mylar-film cage (17-cm-long, 2.5-cm diam) to serve as a mechanically excluded, disease-free check. Seedboxes were infested at 10 viruliferous nymphs/seedling for a 3-4 h inoculation feeding. To ensure efficient disease transmission, nymphs were disturbed manually at hourly intervals so that they were uniformly redistributed among the seedlings.

1. Synchronized tungro resistance screening activities using viruliferous GLH nymphs. IRRI, 1990.

At the end of inoculation feeding, the seedbox was covered with a 120- × 70- × 35-cm wooden-frame, mylar-film cage with 2-mm-thick, 20-cm-long galvanized-iron wires hanging vertically from the roof of the cage 10 cm apart. The iron tray was filled with water (water level increased at 2 cm/min). As the water level rose, the nymphs gradually moved toward seedling tips and transferred to the overhanging wires. When seedlings were submerged in 5-cm water, the cage was raised and the seedbox gently pulled out. The small cages enclosing the check seedlings were removed.

Another seedbox with fresh seedlings was slid under the cage, water in the iron tray was siphoned out, and the cage was lowered. The cage top was tapped to dislodge the nymphs hanging from the wires and ceiling onto fresh seedlings.

After virus transmission in two batches of seedlings, nymphs were allowed to feed overnight on tungro-infected plants to reacquire the virus.

Seedlings exposed to viruliferous nymphs were compared with control

seedling 3 wk after inoculation and scored on percentage of infected plants.

Two batches of viruliferous nymphs a week can be produced on tungro-infected source plants in an oviposition cage (Fig. 1). The first batch consists of nymphs emerging from eggs laid Mon to Fri; the second, from eggs laid Fri to Mon. Each batch can be used for 2-3 daily inoculations for 5 d. Older nymphs are transferred to TN1 plants in pre-oviposition cages; emerging adults are transferred to oviposition cages to restart the culture.

Using this method, we have screened more than 4,000 germplasm collections and advanced breeding lines. Two accessions of *Oryza latifolia* (IRRI Acc. nos. 105141 and 105142) and one accession of *Oryza officinalis* (IRRI Acc. no. 105220) showed tungro resistance.

To differentiate stunting due to insect feeding from stunting caused by tungro infection, IR29 (vector-resistant but tungro-susceptible) and TN1 (susceptible to both vector and tungro) seedlings were infested for 6 h with 10 or 40

2. Plant height reduction caused by GLH feeding and tungro-infection damage on GLH-resistant IR29 and GLH-susceptible TN1. IRRI, 1990.

viruliferous or nonviruliferous nymphs/seedling. In both cultivars, direct damage by 10 to 40 nymphs/seedling was insignificant. Height reduction due to tungro was significantly higher than that caused by nymphs alone (Fig. 2). ■

Blast (BI) and bacterial blight (BB) reactions in some wild rices

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We tested 33 wild rice accessions from IRRI for reactions to leaf BI (*Pyricularia oryzae*) and leaf BB (*Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*).

To measure BI reactions, entries were grown in the BI nurseries as the IRBN entries are grown and inoculated at 3- to 4-leaf stage with chopped infected leaf pieces as well as with a spore suspension of *P. oryzae*. Nursery beds were irrigated lightly every afternoon and covered with polyethylene sheets at night to maintain high humidity.

To measure BB reactions, entries were grown in pots following normal cultural practices. They were inoculated at the booting stage with isolate Bxo9 of *X. c.* pv. *oryzae* by the clipping method.

Reactions of some wild rices to leaf BI and BB in Bangladesh.

Name	IRRI acc. no.	BI (% DLA)	BB (% DLA)
<i>O. officinalis</i>	100179	—	—
<i>O. barthii</i>	100117	20.0	—
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100962	—	—
<i>O. minuta</i>	101089	8.0	—
<i>O. barthii</i>	101380	20.0	12.2
<i>O. nivara</i>	102171	65.0	21.7
<i>O. officinalis</i>	102460	65.0	16.2
<i>O. nivara</i>	102463	65.0	15.9
<i>O. nivara</i>	102465	8.0	9.8
<i>O. rufipogon/O.nivara</i>	102467	20.0	9.5
<i>O. rufipogon/O.nivara</i>	102468-2	2.0	25.2
<i>O. rufipogon/O.nivara</i>	102468-3	2.0	35.0
<i>O. rufipogon/O.nivara</i>	102468-5	20.0	22.5
<i>O. rufipogon/O.nivara</i>	102468-6	15.0	28.7
<i>O. rufipogon/O.nivara</i>	102468-7	20.0	26.1
<i>O. rufipogon/O.nivara</i>	102468-8	20.0	15.8
<i>O. rufipogon/O.nivara</i>	102471	20.0	14.8
<i>O. rufipogon/O.nivara</i>	103406	15.0	6.4
<i>O. nivara</i>	103821	40.0	15.8
<i>O. nivara</i>	103826	—	20.2
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	103827-1	35.0	27.6
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	103827-2	40.0	33.2
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	103828	20.0	21.1
Hybrid Swamp	103829	60.0	33.1
<i>O. nivara</i>	103830	65.0	—
<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	103831	65.0	—
<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	103833	20.0	—
<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	103834	65.0	—
<i>O. nivara</i>	103835	60.0	—
<i>O. nivara</i>	103836	15.0	22.0
<i>O. nivara</i>	103837-1	2.0	25.7
<i>O. nivara</i>	103837-2	2.0	20.6
<i>O. nivara</i>	103840-1	1.0	12.7